
MARKETING, ITS TASKS AND TYPES

Saitov Siroj Abduvaliyevich¹

Najmiddinov Dilshod Rafiddin ugli²

Abdihomidov Zarif Sherzod ugli³

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

In this article we will make a research about the concept, content and essence of marketing, about its goals and objectives, types, about the advantages of marketing, about the role it currently occupies in the eyes of the world community, for what purpose it is used.

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¹ Assitant, Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan, UZB

² Intern, Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan, UZB

³ Student, Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan, UZB

MARKETING, UNING VAZIFALARI VA TURLARI

KALIT SO‘ZLAR:

marketing faoliyati,
marketolog, foyda olish,
iste'molchi, maksimal yuqori
iste'molga erishish,
marketing afzalliklari,
jamiyat boyligi

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada marketing tushunchasi, mazmun-mohiyati haqida, uning maqsad va vazifalari, turlari haqida, marketingning afzalliklari, hozirgi kunda dunyo hamjamiyati oldida tutgan o'rnini haqida, nima maqsadda foydalanilishi haqida so'z boradi.

Hozirgi kunda dunyo bo'ylab dolzarb masalalar, turli muammolar yuzaga kelmoqda, yangidan yangi kashfiyotlar qilinmoqda. Bundan tashqari, zamon o'zgargan sayin hayot murakkablashmoqda, yashash qiyinlashmoqda. Ishlab chiqarish hajmi kun sayin ortib bormoqda. Bu davrda endi hamma o'zi uchun o'zi harakat qilishi kerak. Shunda savol tug'iladi: Ishlab chiqarishni tashkil qilish va uni yuritish uchun nima qilish kerak?

Ishlab chiqarishni tashkil qilishdan oldin, dastlab, bozorni o'rganish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi. Bozorni o'rganishda marketing bo'yicha bilim va ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lishi kerak.

Marketing atamasi dastlab 1902 yilda AQShda paydo bo'lgan, 20 yildan keyin esa bu atamadan jahonning ko'pgina mamlakatlari foydalana boshladilar. Marketing (marketing) "bozor bilan bog'liq faoliyat" ma'nosini anglatadi. Lekin bu tushunchaning ma'nosi juda kengdir.

Marketing tushunchasiga ko'plab iqtisodchi olimlar, marketologlar o'z fikrlarini bildirishgan.

Joel Evans va Barriy Bermanlar marketingga quyidagicha ta'rif berganlar: "Marketing – Tovar, xizmat, tashkilot, hudud va g'oyalarga bo'lgan talabni oldindan bilish, boshqarish va qondirishdir."

Berni Gudrich: "Marketing – bu iste'molchilarning ehtiyoj va istaklarini aniqlash, bashorat qilish va yaratish. Kompaniyaning barcha resurslarini kompaniya va iste'molchi uchun katta foyda bilan qondirish uchun tashkil etish jarayonidir" deya ta'rif bergan.

Filipp Kotler ham marketing haqida o'z fikrini bayon qilgan: "Marketing – bu takliflarni yaratish va tovarlarni (g'oyalar, xizmatlar va boshqalar) almashish orqali ham jismoniy shaxslar, ham guruhlarining ehtiyojlarini qondirishga qaratilgan ijtimoiy boshqaruv jarayonidir."

Mashhur iqtisodchi Adam Smit XVIII asrning ikkinchi yarmidayoq o'zining "Jamiyat boyligi" nomli kitobida ishlab chiqaruvchining iste'molchining talabini qondirishdan boshqa qayg'usi yo'qdir – deb yozgan edi.

Marketing talabni qondirishga qaratilgan faoliyat bo'libgina qolmay, balki talabga ta'sir ham qilishdir. Talab marketing maqsadini, shu bilan birga kerakli marketing strategiyasini tanlashga imkon beradi.

Marketing sohasidagi adabiyotlarda asosan marketingning to'rtta maqsadi keltiriladi:

1. Mumkin bo'lgan maksimal yuqori iste'molga erishish;
2. Iste'molchilarga talabining maksimal qondirilishiga erishish;
3. Iste'molchilarga keng assortimentdagi tovarlarni tanlashiga imkoniyat yaratish;
4. Aholi turmush darajasi sifatini oshirish.

Ko'pchilik rahbarlar marketingning – ishlab chiqarishning maksimal o'sishi va korxonaning boyishida asosiy omil yuqori iste'molga erishini rag'batlantirishda deb biladilar. Bu fikrni boshqacha ifodalasak, odamlar qancha ko'p sotib olsa va qancha ko'p iste'mol qilishsa, shuncha baxtli bo'ladilar degan ma'noni anglatadi. Lekin, ba'zi bir kishilar moddiy boyliklar masalasining ortishi katta baxtga erishishdan dalolatdir degan fikrga shubha bilan qaraydilar. Demak marketingning maqsadi faqat mumkin bo'lgan maksimal iste'molga erishishdangina iborat emas ekan.

Marketing tizimining asosiy maqsadi mumkin bo'lgan maksimal yuqori iste'molga erishish emas, balki iste'molchilarning talabini maksimal qondirishdan iboratdir. Bu degani tovar massasi iste'moli ko'p bo'lsada, u biron-bir ahamiyatga ega bo'lmasligi mumkin. Ularning ahamiyatligi, tovar massasining ko'pligi bilan emas, balki bu tovar massalarning qanchalik darajada iste'molchilarning talabini qondira olishi bilan o'lchanadi. Afsuski, iste'molchilarning talabining qondirilish darajasini o'rganish to hozirgi kungacha muammoligacha qolmoqda.

Ko'pchilik mutaxassislar marketing tizimining asosiy maqsadi aholi "turmush darajasining sifati" ni yaxshilashdan iborat deb biladilar.

Umumiy holda marketingning asosiy maqsadi, uning vujudga kelish, shakllanish va rivojlanishning ob'ektiv sabablari, zarurati bilan belgilanadi.

Marketing ishlab chiqarishni xaridor ehtiyojiga moslashtirib, talab va taklifni muvozanatiga erishgan holda, uni tashkil etgan korxonalar tashkilotlarga yuqori foyda keltirishdir. Bunga erishish uchun marketing quyidagi muhim vazifalarni hal etmog'i lozim:

- Xaridorlar ehtiyojini o'rganish va aniqlash;
- Tovarlarga bo'lgan ichki va tashqi talabni o'rganish;
- Korxonaning faoliyatini xaridorlar ehtiyojiga moslashtirish;
- Avvalo talab va taklif to'g'risida olingan ma'lumotlar asosida bozorni o'rganish;
- Tovarlar reklamasini tashkil etish, xaridorlarni tovarlarni sotib olishga qiziqtirishini oshirish;
- Tovarni bozorga chiqarishdagi barcha xizmatlar to'g'risida ma'lumot olish;
- To'ldiruvchi tovarlar va o'rnini bosuvchi tovarlar to'g'risida axborotlar yig'ish.

Marketingning aniq shakllari va mazmuni korxonalar faoliyati xususiyatlaridan, uning ichki imkoniyatlari va tashqi shart sharoitlaridan kelib chiqadi. Bu yerda marketing va boshqa hamma oraliq faoliyat turlarining qo'yilgan maqsadlarga erishish uchun yagona

yo'naltiriladigan jarayonga birlashishi sodir bo'ladi, bu esa o'z navbatida turli xil marketing turlarining harakatlashini belgilab beradi.

Marketingning quyidagi turlarini keltirish mumkin:

1. Amal qilish davri;
 - 1.1. Strategik marketing
 - 1.2. Taktik marketing
2. Amal qilish sohasi;
 - 2.1. Jamoatchilik xususiyatiga ega bo'lgan g'oyalar marketing
 - 2.2. Joylar marketing
 - 2.3. Ichki marketing
 - 2.4. Tashkilotlar marketing
 - 2.5. Xalqaro marketing
3. Faoliyat turi;
 - 3.1. Moliyaviy marketing
 - 3.2. Innovatsion marketing
 - 3.3. Sanoat marketingi
 - 3.4. Xizmatlar sohasidagi marketing
4. Ta'sir etish usuli;
 - 4.1. To'g'ri marketing
 - 4.2. Television marketing
 - 4.3. Pochta orqali marketing
 - 4.4. Katolog bo'yicha marketing
5. Bozorning rivojlanish darajasi;
 - 5.1. Passiv marketing
 - 5.2. Tashkiliy marketing
 - 5.3. Faol marketing

Marketing turlari o'rtasida muayyan bog'liqlik mavjud. U marketing jarayonlarini har tomonlama va aniq vaziyatda ko'rib chiqishga imkon beradi.

Marketing faoliyatini yuritishning bir qator afzalliklarini keltirish mumkin. Korxonaning asosiy ish yurituvchi sifatida marketologni olishimiz mumkin. Chunki istalgan korxonada ish faoliyatini davom ettirish uchun marketingga alohida e'tibor berishi lozim. Marketing bor joyda o'sish bo'ladi, rivojlanish bo'ladi. Marketing orqali korxonada yoki tashkilotlar o'z raqobatchilari bilan raqobatlasha olishi, ishlab chiqarayotgan mahsulotini sotishi, o'ziga xaridorlarni jalb qila olishi mumkin.

Marketingning dunyo hamjamiyati oldidagi o'rni beqiyos desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Chunki marketingni korxonada yoki tashkilot yuragi deb olsak, o'sha korxonada va tashkilotlar jamiyat ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun xizmat qiladi. Marketing iste'molchilar ehtiyojini qondirish maqsadida bozorni o'rganib, tadbirkorni to'g'ri yo'lga boshlaydi. Bundan jamiyat manfaat ko'radi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, marketing orqali xaridorni u xohlagan

narsa bilan ta'minlab, bunda oqilona narx belgilab, tovarlarni unga qulay bo'lgan joyda va kerakli miqdorda xarid qilish imkoniyatini berish orqali muvaffaqiyatga erishish mumkin. Bundan tashqari marketing bo'lmasdan turib, tadbirkorlik faoliyatini yuritish mushkul. Yuqorida qayd etilganidek, marketing bozorni o'rganish, tartibga solish va boshqarish tizimidir. Marketingni tadbirkorlikning bir bo'g'ini desak adashmagan bo'lamiz.

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